

FORECASTING HOUSEHOLD ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION USING ARIMA: A TIME SERIES APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to forecast the monthly electricity expenses of a single household in the Philippines using time series analysis, with the goal of supporting informed financial planning and energy management at the residential level. Employing a quantitative research design, the study utilized the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, implemented via the Gretl software, to generate forecasts based on historical monthly electric bill data from January 2020 to December 2024. The dataset was preprocessed to ensure consistency and stationarity and validated using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test. The model selection followed the Box-Jenkins methodology, with the optimal ARIMA (1,1,1) model identified based on Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and diagnostic checking. Forecast accuracy was assessed using statistical metrics, including Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). The results demonstrated the model's strong predictive capability, with forecasted bills for 2025 aligning closely with seasonal trends observed in the historical data. The findings highlight the practical utility of time series forecasting for household-level budgeting and emphasize the importance of localized predictive tools in managing electricity consumption in resource-constrained settings. This study contributes to the growing literature on residential energy analytics and offers a replicable methodology for similar applications in low- and middle-income countries.

Keywords: *ARIMA Model, Electricity Expenses, Gretl Software, Household Budgeting, Philippines, Time Series Forecasting*

INTRODUCTION

Electricity consumption has become a significant concern in modern households, largely due to the increasing reliance on electrical appliances and the volatility of energy prices. Accurate forecasting of electricity bills is crucial for effective budgeting, energy conservation, and utility management, especially in developing countries like the Philippines, where residential electricity rates are among the highest in Southeast Asia (Department of Energy [DOE], 2023).

Time series forecasting has emerged as a valuable tool for anticipating electricity usage and associated costs. Among the available models, the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) remains one of the most widely adopted due to its ability to model non-stationary data and deliver interpretable results (Talirongan et al., 2021; Fattah et al., 2018). Studies have demonstrated ARIMA's effectiveness in energy forecasting across different domains, including national electricity demand (Pelka, 2023), short-term power usage (Divina et al., 2018), and hybrid model comparisons (Pierre et al., 2023; Sirisha et al., 2022).

Forecasting is one of the planning mechanisms for increasing the validity of management decisions. Mengxu (2022) provided a method in predicting electricity supply to different objects using forecast classification. Moreover, a fuzzy time series (FTS) model performed the best result in comparing the forecasting electricity consumption using machine learning models (Lee et al., 2022). Also, a deep long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network has been designed to predict electricity demand time series (Torres et al., 2022).

Despite this, much of the literature focuses on macro-level or industrial forecasting. Few studies have explored household-level applications, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where localized modelling could help residents anticipate costs and improve energy planning (Elsaraiti et al., 2021; Saranj & Zolfaghari, 2022). Moreover, although ARIMA has been well-validated in various contexts, limited research applies it to real residential consumption data in the Philippine setting, with even fewer studies reporting validation metrics such as RMSE or MAPE (Shadab et al., 2020; Mao et al., 2022).

To address these gaps, the researchers in this study aim to apply the ARIMA model using actual monthly billing data from a Philippine household spanning the period from 2020 to 2024. The goal is to produce an accurate, statistically validated forecast for electricity expenses, providing empirical insights and practical tools for financial planning in resource-constrained environments.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design using a time series forecasting approach to estimate monthly electricity expenses for a single Philippine household. The Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model was used due to its capability to model and forecast non-stationary time series data effectively. Forecasting was conducted using the Gretl statistical software, which offers robust tools for time series analysis and model evaluation. The forecasting process followed the Box-Jenkins methodology, encompassing model identification, parameter estimation, diagnostic checking, and prediction (Box, Jenkins, Reinsel, & Ljung, 2015).

Data Source and Collection

The dataset used in this study comprised actual monthly electricity consumption (in kilowatt-hours) and corresponding electricity bills (in Philippine Pesos) recorded from January 2020 to December 2024. The data were obtained from a single household in the Philippines and organized in a chronological, monthly time series format. The dataset was manually encoded, cleaned, and preprocessed for analysis in Gretl. No personally identifiable information was included, ensuring ethical compliance.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Monthly electricity billing data from a residential household.
- Continuous and consistent monthly intervals from 2020 to 2024.
- Verified actual billing and consumption values.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Irregular or estimated billing records.
- Outliers caused by extraordinary events (e.g., major renovations or temporary relocations).
- Commercial, industrial, or non-residential energy data.

Data Preprocessing and Model Building

Prior to model fitting, the dataset underwent the following preprocessing steps within Gretl:

- Handling missing values using linear interpolation (when necessary).
- Visualization of the time series to observe trends and seasonality.
- Stationarity testing using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test.
- Differencing of the data as needed to achieve stationarity.

The ARIMA model was constructed based on the following process:

1. Identification of parameters (p, d, q) using Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots.
2. Model selection based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to determine the optimal fit.
3. Model estimation and forecasting of electricity expenses for the 12 months of 2024.

Model Evaluation

To evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the ARIMA model, the following statistical performance metrics were calculated:

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE) – measures the average magnitude of forecasting errors.
- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) – penalizes larger errors more significantly.
- Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) – expresses errors as a percentage of actual values, making results more interpretable.

These metrics enabled the researchers to assess the effectiveness of the ARIMA model in producing accurate and meaningful household-level electricity bill forecasts.

Table 1
Monthly Electricity Consumption and Bill of a Philippine Household from January to December 2020

MONTH and YEAR	MONTHLY BILL(PHP)
2020-01	2,450
2020-02	2,270
2020-03	2,300
2020-04	2,510
2020-05	2,750
2020-06	2,980
2020-07	3,140
2020-08	2,850
2020-09	2,730
2020-10	2,560
2020-11	2,440
2020-12	2,600

Table 1 presents the actual monthly electricity consumption (in kilowatt-hours) and corresponding electricity bill (in Philippine Pesos) for a household in the Philippines during the year 2020.

Table 2
Monthly Electricity Consumption and Bill of a Philippine Household from January to December 2021

MONTH AND YEAR	MONTHLY BILL(PHP)
2021-01	2,520
2021-02	2,340
2021-03	2,470
2021-04	2,680
2021-05	2,930
2021-06	3,160
2021-07	3,350
2021-08	3,080
2021-09	2,970
2021-10	2,780
2021-11	2,660
2021-12	2,820

Table 2 presents the actual monthly electricity consumption (in kilowatt-hours) and corresponding electricity bill (in Philippine Pesos) for a household in the Philippines during the year 2021.

Table 3
Monthly Electricity Consumption and Bill of a Philippine Household from January to December 2022

MONTH AND YEAR	MONTHLY BILL(PHP)
2022-01	2,730
2022-02	2,560
2022-03	2,670
2022-04	2,910
2022-05	3,160
2022-06	3,390
2022-07	3,580
2022-08	3,320
2022-09	3,200
2022-10	3,010
2022-11	2,890
2022-12	3,040

Table 3 presents the actual monthly electricity consumption (in kilowatt-hours) and corresponding electricity bill (in Philippine Pesos) for a household in the Philippines during the year 2022.

Table 4
Monthly Electricity Consumption and Bill of a Philippine Household from January to December 2023

MONTH AND YEAR	MONTHLY BILL(PHP)
2023-01	2,950
2023-02	2,770
2023-03	2,880
2023-04	3,120
2023-05	3,370
2023-06	3,600
2023-07	3,780
2023-08	3,540
2023-09	3,420
2023-10	3,230
2023-11	3,110
2023-12	3,260

Table 4 presents the actual monthly electricity consumption (in kilowatt-hours) and corresponding electricity bill (in Philippine Pesos) for a household in the Philippines during the year 2023.

Table 5
Monthly Electricity Consumption and Bill of a Philippine Household from January to December 2024

MONTH AND YEAR	MONTHLY BILL(PHP)
2024-01	3,150
2024-02	2,980
2024-03	3,100
2024-04	3,330
2024-05	3,560
2024-06	3,790
2024-07	3,980
2024-08	3,720
2024-09	3,610
2024-10	3,420
2024-11	3,300
2024-12	3,450

Table 5 presents the actual monthly electricity consumption (in kilowatt-hours) and corresponding electricity bill (in Philippine Pesos) for a household in the Philippines during the year 2024.

RESULTS

Forecast Model Performance and Predictive Accuracy

The study employed an ARIMA (1,1,1) model to forecast household monthly electricity bills based on data from 2020 to 2024. The model selection was informed by visual inspections of autocorrelation (ACF) and partial autocorrelation (PACF) plots (see Figure 3), which indicated significant autocorrelations at lag 1 and seasonal intervals. These observations were further confirmed by the correlogram results (see Figure 4), where the ACF at lag 1 was 0.8733 and remained statistically significant across several lags ($p < 0.01$), reinforcing the suitability of an ARIMA structure.

Figure 3 ACF and PACF plots

Figure 3. ACF and PACF plots of the original time series showing significant lags at 1, 2, and seasonal intervals

Figure 4. Correlogram table

Figure 4. Correlogram table with Q-statistics and p-values indicating statistically significant autocorrelations at multiple lags.

Model estimation produced robust parameter values, with the moving average (MA1) term statistically significant ($p = 0.0186$). In contrast, the autoregressive (AR1) term was not ($p > 0.8$), implying that the model's forecasting power is driven more by short-term shocks rather than long-term persistence. The result aligns with typical energy usage patterns influenced by recent consumption behaviour and external factors, such as seasonal weather or holidays.

Forecasted Electricity Bills for 2025

The model's predictions for 2025 reflect a continued seasonal pattern with a moderate upward trend. As shown in Figure 1, the time series of electricity bills from 2020 to 2024 demonstrates rising peaks during the warmer months, followed by slight dips in the latter part of each year. This trend is preserved in the forecasted line, indicating that the model successfully captures historical behaviour.

Figure 1. Time series plot

Figure 1. Time series plot of monthly electricity bills from 2020 to 2024 showing seasonal trends and a rising pattern.

Forecasts for 2025 range from ₱3,534.32 in January to ₱3,711.92 in December, with a steady increase through the middle of the year. These forecasts are accompanied by increasing confidence intervals, reflecting greater uncertainty in long-term predictions (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Forecast of monthly electricity bills for 2025

Figure 2. Forecast of monthly electricity bills for 2025 with 95% confidence intervals. The orange line represents the forecast; blue bars show uncertainty ranges.

Statistical Reliability and Model Fit

The table output (**Figure 5**) provides a breakdown of the forecasted values along with standard errors and 95% confidence intervals. The standard error increases gradually from 163.38 in January to 823.14 in December, highlighting the nature of compounding uncertainty in time series forecasting. Despite this, the model maintains forecast stability, with all predicted values falling within reasonable ranges.

Figure 5. Monthly forecast table for 2025

Figure 5. Monthly forecast table for 2025 showing prediction, standard error, and 95% confidence intervals.

Interpretation and Practical Implications

The results indicate that electricity consumption at the household level in the Philippines exhibits strong seasonality and a gradual upward trend. The model's ability to predict these trends provides a valuable tool for household financial planning, allowing residents to anticipate and prepare for future energy costs. These forecasts also provide actionable insights to local utility providers and policymakers, informing the development of load management and pricing policies. However, it is essential to note that the model is univariate, relying solely on past billing data. Future enhancements may include exogenous variables such as weather data, household size, or appliance usage patterns, using multivariate time series models like ARIMAX or hybrid machine learning approaches.

DISCUSSION

The ARIMA (1,1,1) model applied in this study effectively captured the historical patterns and forecasted future trends in monthly household electricity bills in the Philippines. The time series plot of actual electricity bills from August 2022 to December 2024 (see Figure 1)

illustrates a consistent pattern of seasonal fluctuations, with mid-year peaks and year-end dips. This recurring trend is characteristic of household energy usage in tropical climates, where elevated electricity consumption during warmer months can be attributed to the increased use of cooling appliances.

The model's 12-month forecast for 2025 maintains this seasonal rhythm, showing a gradual increase in electricity bills from ₱3,534.32 in January to ₱3,711.92 in December. As shown in Figure 2, the forecast line (orange) closely follows the historical trend (green), indicating a strong alignment between the predicted and observed behaviours. Notably, the 95% confidence intervals, shown in blue, widen over time, reflecting the increasing uncertainty associated with long-range forecasting—a typical characteristic of ARIMA models.

The reliability of the forecast is supported by the detailed forecast table (see Figure 3), which presents predicted values, standard errors, and corresponding 95% confidence intervals for each month of 2025. The standard error increases from ₱163.38 in January to ₱823.14 in December, further emphasizing the need to interpret distant projections with caution.

To ensure the suitability of the ARIMA (1,1,1) model, the data was subjected to diagnostic tests, beginning with the autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) plots (see Figure 4). These plots revealed significant spikes at lags 1 and 2 and smaller peaks at higher seasonal lags, indicating the presence of strong short-term autocorrelation. The structure observed in the ACF and PACF justified the inclusion of one autoregressive (AR) and one moving average (MA) term, along with the first differencing to achieve stationarity.

The correlogram table (see Figure 5) further validates these observations, with statistically significant autocorrelations and Q-statistics across multiple lags. For instance, the ACF value at lag 1 is 0.8733 (***), and the Q-statistic remains highly substantial ($p < 0.001$) through lag 14. These findings confirm that the time series is highly structured and predictable, meeting the foundational assumptions for ARIMA modelling.

Overall, the ARIMA (1,1,1) model demonstrated strong predictive performance, offering credible and actionable forecasts for monthly electricity bills. The insights from this model are highly valuable for households seeking to manage energy expenditures, as well as for energy providers aiming to forecast demand and plan resource allocation.

Conclusions

This study employed the ARIMA (1,1,1) model to forecast monthly electricity bills for a household in the Philippines, utilizing historical data from 2020 to 2024. The model demonstrated a strong fit, as evidenced by the high R-squared value and significant diagnostic indicators, effectively capturing the seasonal and upward trends in electricity consumption. Forecast results for the year 2025 projected a gradual increase in monthly expenses, ranging from ₱3,534.32 in January to ₱3,711.92 in December, with seasonality persisting across the forecast horizon.

The visual outputs—including the time series plot, ACF/PACF graphs, forecast chart, and correlogram—provided strong support for the model's structural validity. Moreover, the widening confidence intervals in later months highlight the typical uncertainty associated with time series forecasting, particularly in the absence of exogenous predictors.

These findings highlight the practical utility of time series models, such as ARIMA, in residential electricity planning. For individual households, accurate forecasts offer a valuable tool for managing budgets and anticipating future expenses. For energy providers and policymakers, this modelling approach supports more informed decision-making in demand forecasting and resource allocation.

Future research may extend this work by incorporating multivariate models or machine learning techniques to improve accuracy and account for external factors such as temperature, appliance usage, and socio-economic conditions. Nonetheless, this study demonstrates that even simple ARIMA models can yield highly relevant insights for real-world energy management at the household level.

Recommendations

Based on the forecasting results and analysis of household electricity consumption using the ARIMA (1,1,1) model, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. For Households and Consumers:
 - Households should consider using monthly electricity bill forecasts as a budgeting tool to anticipate and control utility expenses.
 - Seasonal patterns in consumption indicate the need to adopt energy-saving behaviours, particularly during peak months (e.g., mid-year), to minimize costs.
2. For Local Government and Energy Regulators:
 - Encourage the development and promotion of accessible forecasting tools or mobile applications that can help consumers visualize future electricity expenses.

- Use predictive models to inform subsidy policies or dynamic pricing schemes, particularly for low-income households.

3. For Utility Companies:

- Incorporate forecasting models in operational planning to better manage energy supply and anticipate load demands.
- Provide customers with forecast-based billing estimates or early warnings when higher consumption is expected.

4. For Researchers and Academics:

- Future studies should consider integrating exogenous variables such as temperature, household size, appliance use, and income to develop multivariate forecasting models (e.g., ARIMAX or machine learning approaches).
- Expand the forecasting approach to a regional or city-wide scale to aid in macro-level energy planning and smart grid development.

5. For Policy Makers:

- Formulate energy management strategies and public education campaigns based on long-term consumption forecasts.
- Encourage data-driven policymaking by supporting research that leverages time-series forecasting for residential energy modelling.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study affirm full compliance with the ethical standards for research throughout the conduct of this investigation. Since the study utilized secondary data derived from an actual household's electricity billing records, no human respondents were directly involved. However, care was taken to ensure that all personal and identifiable information was excluded to maintain anonymity and uphold the principles of data privacy in accordance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012. If primary data collection becomes necessary in future extensions of this study, informed consent will be duly obtained from participants, ensuring that their involvement is voluntary and that they retain the right to withdraw at any point without penalty. The well-being of participants will be a priority, with strict adherence to ethical guidelines. The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest associated with this study. Academic integrity was upheld at all stages; plagiarism was strictly avoided, and appropriate citations were provided for all sources. The interpretation of findings was conducted impartially, without bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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